

Site covariate: P_Area_log

Random effect

Site covariate: D_2_Core

Random effect

Site covariate: Canopy

Random effect

Site covariate: D_2_PA

Random effect

Site covariate: HMI

Random effect

Site covariate: VNL_2

Random effect

Site covariate: Elev

Random effect

Site covariate: NPP

Random effect

Site covariate: Precip

Random effect

